

THE SLIDING MODE CONTROLLER DESIGN FOR HYBRID SYNCHRONIZATION OF PAN SYSTEMS

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the hybrid synchronization of identical Pan systems (Pan, Xu and Zhou, 2010) by sliding mode control. In hybrid synchronization of chaotic systems, one part of the master and slave systems is completely synchronized, while the other part is anti-synchronized. The co-existence of complete and anti-synchronization enhances the security of the communication devices using chaotic systems. The stability results derived in this paper for the hybrid synchronization of identical Pan systems are established using Lyapunov stability theory. Since the Lyapunov exponents are not required for these calculations, the sliding mode control method is very effective and convenient to achieve hybrid synchronization of the identical Pan systems. Numerical simulations are shown to illustrate and validate the hybrid synchronization schemes derived in this paper for the identical Pan systems.

KEYWORDS

Sliding Mode Control, Hybrid Synchronization, Chaotic Systems, Pan System.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nonlinear dynamical systems, which are highly sensitive to initial conditions, are called as chaotic systems. The sensitive nature of chaotic systems is known as the *butterfly effect* [1]. Chaos theory has been applied in many scientific disciplines such as Mathematics, Computer Science, Microbiology, Biology, Ecology, Economics, Population Dynamics and Robotics.

Synchronization of chaotic systems is a phenomenon which may occur when two or more chaotic oscillators are coupled or when a chaotic oscillator drives another chaotic oscillator. Because of the butterfly effect, this is a challenging problem in the control literature.

In most of the chaos synchronization approaches, the *master-slave* or *drive-response* formalism is used. If a particular chaotic system is called the *master* or *drive* system and another chaotic system is called the *slave* or *response* system, then the idea of the anti-synchronization is to use the output of the master system to control the slave system so that the states of the slave system have the same amplitude but opposite signs as the states of the master system asymptotically.

Since the pioneering work by Pecora and Carroll ([2], 1990), chaos synchronization problem has been studied extensively and intensively in the literature [2-17]. Chaos theory has been applied to a variety of fields such as physical systems [3], chemical systems [4], ecological systems [5], secure communications [6-8], etc. In the hybrid synchronization of chaotic systems, one part of

the master-slave systems is completely synchronized, while the other part is anti-synchronized. The co-existence of complete synchronization (CS) and anti-synchronization (AS) in the synchronization process is found to be highly useful in secure communication devices.

In the last two decades, various schemes have been successfully applied for chaos synchronization such as PC method [2], OGY method [9], active control method [10-14], adaptive control method [15-20], time-delay feedback method [21], backstepping design method [22], sampled-data feedback method [23], etc.

In this paper, we derive new results based on the sliding mode control [24-28] for the hybrid synchronization of identical Pan systems ([29], Pan, 2010). In robust control systems, the sliding mode control method is often adopted due to its inherent advantages of easy realization, fast response and good transient performance as well as its insensitivity to parameter uncertainties and external disturbances.

This paper has been organized as follows. In Section 2, we describe the problem statement and our methodology using sliding mode control (SMC). In Section 3, we discuss the hybrid synchronization of identical Pan systems. In Section 4, we summarize the main results obtained in this paper.

2. PROBLEM STATEMENT AND OUR METHODOLOGY USING SMC

In this section, we describe the problem statement for the hybrid synchronization for identical chaotic systems and our methodology using sliding mode control (SMC).

Consider the chaotic system described by

$$\dot{x} = Ax + f(x) \tag{1}$$

where $x \in R^n$ is the state of the system, A is the $n \times n$ matrix of the system parameters and $f : R^n \rightarrow R^n$ is the nonlinear part of the system.

We consider the system (1) as the *master* or *drive* system.

As the *slave* or *response* system, we consider the following chaotic system described by the dynamics

$$\dot{y} = Ay + f(y) + u \tag{2}$$

where $y \in R^n$ is the state of the system and $u \in R^m$ is the controller to be designed.

We define the *hybrid synchronization error* as

$$e_i = \begin{cases} y_i - x_i, & \text{if } i \text{ is odd} \\ y_i + x_i, & \text{if } i \text{ is even} \end{cases} \tag{3}$$

then the error dynamics is obtained as

$$\dot{e} = Ae + \eta(x, y) + u, \tag{4}$$

The objective of the global chaos synchronization problem is to find a controller u such that

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \|e(t)\| = 0 \quad \text{for all } e(0) \in \mathbb{R}^n. \quad (5)$$

To solve this problem, we first define the control u as

$$u = -\eta(x, y) + Bv \quad (6)$$

where B is a constant gain vector selected such that (A, B) is controllable.

Substituting (6) into (4), the error dynamics simplifies to

$$\dot{e} = Ae + Bv \quad (7)$$

which is a linear time-invariant control system with single input v . Thus, the original hybrid synchronization problem can be replaced by an equivalent problem of stabilizing the zero solution $e = 0$ of the system (7) by a suitable choice of the sliding mode control.

In the sliding mode control, we define the variable

$$s(e) = Ce = c_1e_1 + c_2e_2 + \dots + c_n e_n \quad (8)$$

where $C = [c_1 \quad c_2 \quad \dots \quad c_n]$ is a constant row vector to be determined.

In the sliding mode control, we constrain the motion of the system (7) to the sliding manifold defined by

$$S = \{x \in \mathbb{R}^n \mid s(e) = 0\}$$

which is required to be invariant under the flow of the error dynamics (7).

When in sliding manifold S , the system (7) satisfies the following conditions:

$$s(e) = 0 \quad (9)$$

which is the defining equation for the manifold S and

$$\dot{s}(e) = 0 \quad (10)$$

which is the necessary condition for the state trajectory $e(t)$ of (7) to stay on the sliding manifold S .

Using (7) and (8), the equation (10) can be rewritten as

$$\dot{s}(e) = C[Ae + Bv] = 0 \quad (11)$$

Solving (11) for v , we obtain the equivalent control law

$$v_{eq}(t) = -(CB)^{-1}CA e(t) \quad (12)$$

where C is chosen such that $CB \neq 0$.

Substituting (12) into the error dynamics (7), we obtain the closed-loop dynamics as

$$\dot{e} = [I - B(CB)^{-1}C]Ae \quad (13)$$

The row vector C is selected such that the system matrix of the controlled dynamics $[I - B(CB)^{-1}C]A$ is Hurwitz, *i.e.* it has all eigenvalues with negative real parts. Then the controlled system (13) is globally asymptotically stable.

To design the sliding mode controller for (7), we apply the constant plus proportional rate reaching law

$$\dot{s} = -q \operatorname{sgn}(s) - k s \quad (14)$$

where $\operatorname{sgn}(\cdot)$ denotes the sign function and the gains $q > 0$, $k > 0$ are determined such that the sliding condition is satisfied and sliding motion will occur.

From equations (11) and (14), we can obtain the control $v(t)$ as

$$v(t) = -(CB)^{-1} [C(kI + A)e + q \operatorname{sgn}(s)] \quad (15)$$

which yields

$$v(t) = \begin{cases} -(CB)^{-1} [C(kI + A)e + q], & \text{if } s(e) > 0 \\ -(CB)^{-1} [C(kI + A)e - q], & \text{if } s(e) < 0 \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

Theorem 1. *The master system (1) and the slave system (2) are globally and asymptotically hybrid synchronized for all initial conditions $x(0), y(0) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ by the feedback control law*

$$u(t) = -\eta(x, y) + Bv(t) \quad (17)$$

where $v(t)$ is defined by (15) and B is a column vector such that (A, B) is controllable. Also, the sliding mode gains k, q are positive.

Proof. First, we note that substituting (17) and (15) into the error dynamics (4), we obtain the closed-loop error dynamics as

$$\dot{e} = Ae - B(CB)^{-1} [C(kI + A)e + q \operatorname{sgn}(s)] \quad (18)$$

To prove that the error dynamics (18) is globally asymptotically stable, we consider the candidate Lyapunov function defined by the equation

$$V(e) = \frac{1}{2} s^2(e) \quad (19)$$

Note that

$$V(e) \geq 0 \text{ for all } e \in R^n \text{ and } V(e) = 0 \Leftrightarrow e = 0$$

Thus, it follows that V is a positive definite function on R^n .

Differentiating V along the trajectories of (18) or the equivalent dynamics (14), we get

$$\dot{V}(e) = s(e)\dot{s}(e) = -ks^2 - q\text{sgn}(s)s \quad (20)$$

which is a negative definite function on R^n .

This calculation shows that V is a globally defined, positive definite, Lyapunov function for the error dynamics (18), which has a globally defined, negative definite time derivative \dot{V} .

Thus, by Lyapunov stability theory [37], it is immediate that the error dynamics (18) is globally asymptotically stable for all initial conditions $e(0) \in R^n$.

This means that for all initial conditions $e(0) \in R^n$, we have

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} \|e(t)\| = 0$$

Hence, it follows that the master system (1) and the slave system (2) are globally and asymptotically hybrid-synchronized for all initial conditions $x(0), y(0) \in R^n$.

This completes the proof. ■

3. HYBRID SYNCHRONIZATION OF IDENTICAL PAN SYSTEMS USING SLIDING MODE CONTROL

3.1 Theoretical Results

In this section, we apply the sliding mode control results derived in Section 2 for the hybrid synchronization of identical Pan systems ([29], Pan, 2010).

Thus, the master system is described by the Pan dynamics

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x}_1 &= a(x_2 - x_1) \\ \dot{x}_2 &= cx_1 - x_1x_3 \\ \dot{x}_3 &= -bx_3 + x_1x_2 \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

where x_1, x_2, x_3 are state variables and a, b, c are positive, constant parameters of the system.

The slave system is also described by the Pan dynamics

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{y}_1 &= a(y_2 - y_1) + u_1 \\ \dot{y}_2 &= cy_1 - y_1y_3 + u_2 \\ \dot{y}_3 &= -by_3 + y_1y_2 + u_3\end{aligned}\tag{22}$$

where y_1, y_2, y_3 are state variables and u_1, u_2, u_3 are the controllers to be designed.

The Pan systems (21) and (22) are chaotic when

$$a = 10, \quad b = 8/3 \quad \text{and} \quad c = 16.$$

Figure 1 illustrates the strange chaotic attractor of the chaotic Pan system (21).

Figure 1. Strange Chaotic Attractor of the Pan System

The *hybrid synchronization error* is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} e_1 &= y_1 - x_1 \\ e_2 &= y_2 + x_2 \\ e_3 &= y_3 - x_3 \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

The error dynamics is easily obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{e}_1 &= a(e_2 - e_1) - 2ax_2 + u_1 \\ \dot{e}_2 &= ce_1 + 2cx_1 - y_1y_3 - x_1x_3 + u_2 \\ \dot{e}_3 &= -be_3 + y_1y_2 - x_1x_2 + u_3 \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

We write the error dynamics (24) in the matrix notation as

$$\dot{e} = Ae + \eta(x, y) + u \quad (25)$$

where

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} -a & a & 0 \\ c & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -b \end{bmatrix}, \quad \eta(x, y) = \begin{bmatrix} -2ax_2 \\ 2cx_1 - y_1y_3 - x_1x_3 \\ y_1y_2 - x_1x_2 \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad u = \begin{bmatrix} u_1 \\ u_2 \\ u_3 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (26)$$

The sliding mode controller design is carried out as detailed in Section 2.

First, we set u as

$$u = -\eta(x, y) + Bv \quad (27)$$

where B is chosen such that (A, B) is controllable.

We take B as

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (28)$$

In the chaotic case, the parameter values are chosen as $a = 10$, $b = 8/3$ and $c = 16$.

The sliding mode variable is selected as

$$s = Ce = [6 \quad 6 \quad 1]e = 6e_1 + 6e_2 + e_3 \quad (29)$$

which makes the sliding mode state equation asymptotically stable.

We choose the sliding mode gains as $k = 6$ and $q = 0.1$.

We note that a large value of k can cause chattering and an appropriate value of q is chosen to speed up the time taken to reach the sliding manifold as well as to reduce the system chattering.

From Eq. (15), we can obtain $v(t)$ as

$$v(t) = -5.5385 e_1 - 7.3846e_2 - 0.2564 e_3 - 0.0077 \operatorname{sgn}(s) \quad (30)$$

Thus, the required sliding mode controller is obtained as

$$u = -\eta(x, y) + Bv \quad (31)$$

where $\eta(x, y)$, B and $v(t)$ are defined as in the equations (26), (28) and (30).

By Theorem 2.1, we obtain the following result.

Theorem 3.1. *The identical Pan systems (21) and (22) are globally and asymptotically hybrid synchronized for all initial conditions with the sliding mode controller u defined by (31). ■*

3.2 Numerical Results

In this section For the numerical simulations, the fourth-order Runge-Kutta method with time-step $h = 10^{-6}$ is used to solve the Pan systems (21) and (22) with the sliding mode controller u given by (31) using MATLAB.

In the chaotic case, the parameter values are given by $a = 10$, $b = 8/3$ and $c = 16$.

The sliding mode gains are chosen as $k = 6$ and $q = 0.1$.

The initial values of the master system (21) are taken as

$$x_1(0) = 24, x_2(0) = 12, x_3(0) = -9$$

The initial values of the slave system (22) are taken as

$$y_1(0) = -8, y_2(0) = 20, y_3(0) = 16$$

Figure 2 illustrates the hybrid synchronization of the identical Pan systems (21) and (22).

Figure 3 illustrates the time-history of the anti-synchronization errors e_1, e_2, e_3 .

Figure 2. Hybrid Synchronization of Identical Pan Systems

Figure 3. Time-History of the Hybrid Synchronization Error

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have developed a sliding mode controller (SMC) to achieve hybrid synchronization for the identical Pan systems (2010). Our hybrid synchronization results for the identical Pan systems have been proved using sliding control theory and Lyapunov stability theory. Since the Lyapunov exponents are not required for these calculations, the sliding mode control method is very effective and convenient to achieve hybrid synchronization for the identical Pan systems. Numerical simulations are also shown to illustrate the effectiveness of the hybrid synchronization results derived in this paper using the sliding mode control.

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